

PECULIAR ASPECTS OF WORKING WITH FAMILY IN THE FORMATION OF THE CULTURE OF LIFE SAFETY IN CHILDREN OF PRESCHOOL AGE

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Abstract. *The article presents an analysis of the specific aspects of working with family in the formation of a culture of life safety in children of preschool age.*

Keywords: *parents, security, educators, teaching staff, cooperation, student, initiative, organization, development, pedagogical skill, approach.*

INTRODUCTION

Today, it is one of the urgent tasks to bring up preschool children to be fully developed, physically healthy, mentally mature and spiritually formed. In the implementation of such tasks, "State requirements for the development of primary and preschool children of the Republic of Uzbekistan" determines a number of tasks for comprehensive development of preschool children, education and preparation for school education.

Today, work based on the principle of openness of the preschool education organization for parents is being carried out in our country. According to this principle, parents can freely familiarize themselves with their child's activities, the way the teacher communicates with preschool children about their life safety, and their entry into the group life at their own convenience.

Cooperation of preschool education organizations with social institutions, its openness to the influence of micro-society, that is, "Openness of preschool education organization to the outside" is still one of the activities of preschool education organization today. This principle includes the variability of parents' educational content, forms and methods. In order to ensure the safety of children of preschool age, it is of course important to feel responsible for planning work with the family. Human health is considered the greatest wealth of the country and the state. Therefore, it is not a secret to the people that a number of important works are being carried out in our country to protect people's health and strengthen a healthy lifestyle.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Educating a perfect person, his all-round physical and mental development and forming a healthy way of life are reflected in pedagogical ideas and views of Eastern thinkers Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, Alisher Navai, Husayn Vaiz Koshifi, Jalaluddin Davani, Jalaluddin Rumi, Yusuf Khos Khajib Abdullah Awlani.

P. Yusupova, F.R. Kadirova, R.M. Kadirova, D. Abdurahimova, Kh.B. Tulenova, D.R. Babayeva, G.Kh. Jumasheva, Kh.I. Kasimova, M.SH. Rasulova, M.A. Solihova, K.S. Shodiyeva, SH.A. Sodikova SH. Shodmonova, O.U. Hasanboyeva and others have analyzed the content of activities of preschool educational organizations, the problems of spiritual, moral, physical and psychological upbringing of preschool children. In this field, psychologists scientists G. B. Shoumarov, Ye. A. Morshinina, E. Goziev, V. M. Karimova, M. G. Davletshin, N. A. Soginov, S.

A. Okhunjonova, A. Shojalilov and others have also paid special attention to the issues of child health in their researches.

It is known that, as shown in the researches of V.V. Kolbanova, L.G. Tatarinkova and V.P. Petlenko on the need to use health-saving technologies, more than 60% of a person's health depends on his lifestyle. In fact, a person's living conditions and lifestyle can have a positive or negative effect on his health. Methodological recommendations, such as "Physical development of children" by L. D. Glazyrina, "Physical education for children " by S. Ya. Layzan and T. A. Shorygin's manual "Conversations with children about the basics of safety" contain a lot of theoretical and practical information.

RESULT

Nowadays, all people are equally responsible for the safety of a child's life. A little carelessness can have many negative consequences. There are specific aspects of working with the family to ensure the safety of preschool children. Traffic injuries are one of the serious problems of any city. Unfortunately, every year in our country, children are injured and killed in traffic accidents. We can give examples of the most common mistakes of children: unexpectedly leaving the road in an unknown place and other incidents. When raising a child as a "Disciplined Pedestrian", his first teachers are pedagogues, and his second teachers are family members. In this regard, the establishment of effective cooperation with parents in the organization of work implies the following:

- ✓ Advice for parents;
- ✓ Information stands;
- ✓ Roundtable discussions;
- ✓ Open Debate Day;
- ✓ Visual information design;
- ✓ Additional events with the offer (medical personnel, policeman, fireman);
- ✓ Parent survey and others.

In all activities organized together with parents, the issues of child safety are taken into account. In all forms of such work, it is one of the important conditions for the child to put into practice the knowledge he has acquired about life safety. The main goal of this is that the child learns about the safety of life activities, develops personal characteristics necessary to maintain a healthy lifestyle and ensure safe behavior in dangerous situations, increases the sense of responsibility for personal safety, a valuable attitude to one's health and life, acquires the skills to see potential dangers and to act correctly in case of them, to use personal protective equipment, such knowledge is acquired in the emotional and successful development of preschool children. V.A. Sukhomlinsky emphasized that "How the childhood passed, who led the child by the hand in childhood, what entered his mind and heart from the world around him - this influences on what kind of person today's baby will be".

The problems of ensuring a safe, healthy lifestyle can be solved only by the constant communication of adults and children with equal rights: we look for a way out of a difficult situation together, we discuss the problem together, we communicate, we learn together, we make discoveries, we are surprised

DISCUSSION

Protection of children's lives and strengthening of health in the preschool educational organization is carried out by the pedagogic and medical staff of the preschool educational

organization, as well as by the medical staff of regional health authorities attached to the preschool educational organization, as well as by parents. The fact that children of preschool age spend a whole day in a preschool education organization and ensuring their life safety depends on the employees of PEI implies that they approach their work responsibly. When picking up pupils from a preschool educational institution, the group tutor should hand over the pupil to his parents (a substitute person, adult children of parents, grandparents, or a parent's representative authorized by the parents in accordance with the procedure established by law). It goes without saying that anything neglected can put a child's life at risk. To ensure the safety of children, it is necessary to implement the following: not to leave children alone and unsupervised while they are in a preschool educational institution, to carry out trips or excursions outside the territory of the preschool educational organization in agreement with the internal affairs bodies, to notify the director of the preschool education organization and the parents of the children or their substitutes in case of planned outings or excursions for children outside the territory of the preschool education organization, to install video surveillance devices in MTT, to place an evacuation plan for pupils in case of emergency situations on every floor of the preschool educational organization in places where everyone can see it, the duty officer or night teacher of a preschool with a night group informs the fire authorities about the number of children and staff present in the preschool between 19:00 and 20:00 every day and so on.

CONCLUSION

Thus, a number of reforms are being carried out in the preschool education system today, all of which are one of the measures aimed at serving the interests of children and pedagogues, as well as improving the quality of preschool education. Ensuring social security in preschools, creating a socially safe environment begin with the relationships of staff with each other, with children and their families. Failure is an integral part of learning, even if it does not always feel good. Therefore, children need to feel safe when trying new skills independently or with peers. Your child is now growing older and independent. They like to play in groups and play outside.

A child gets into various life situations in which he can simply get confused. First, it is necessary to give children the necessary knowledge about the norms of behavior generally accepted by people. Secondly, to teach adequate, conscious behavior in a given situation, to help preschool children acquire basic behavioral skills at home, on the street, in the park, in transport, and thirdly, to develop independence and responsibility in preschool children.

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